

Cerebral Cortex Empathic Theory CCE: A Desert of Disingenuous Mental Wellness Illness & Abuse

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Signature of Work

This critical independent research discovery and findings publication created involved many fields of discipline. Some disciplines connected were Arts and Tv media, Business, Government, Education, Behavioral health Science, and social engagement the research lead by scholarly research and real world experience. All Post -Doctoral Research that is original and Independent contribution of knowledge and society. Case studies of real subjects of mental illness unhealthy imbalances included appropriate creative work of documented subjects. The work ranged the last 5+ years constant implemented programs for society heavy intense societal work of Workforce Training and Development, feeding the hungry in underserved, impoverished, and underrepresented communities of children and adults of middle class income earners and below the poverty line residents and those suffering from homeless. Created Nonprofits for city and community service rendered service to population of people regarding basic needs. Food, water, and shelter utilizing a theory implemented continuously had staging and tremendous results meeting multiple facet spheres of life. The fields of Academic, Economic, Spiritual, Moral, Social, and changing people's social economic positioning during this research ages 18-65 years of age. The needs of millions of people in Chicagoland area, and taking research to Los Angeles, California after faced poverty and homelessness head

on. We took on the challenge with determination throughout Southern California. To our findings in our experience called as *Skid Row* over populated shelters referring to the housing epidemic crisis of thousands homeless people living outside and in dilapidated tents and conditions in downtown LA, California, only to find out homeless camps in isolated fields of land or by the storm drains. The discovery given through media stories conducted and interviews of men, women, and children living in horrendous conditions and vilified treatment throughout the SoCal residents desert scarcity behaviors as a drought or famine was happening at the time. This was absolutely fascinating. There has been a bone drought of empathy desperately needed being a wellspring of civility and humanity, and an atmosphere of heightened sense of bitterness, rage, harassment, hostility and anger. The parts of the brain regulate this behavior was monitored and recorded. What was bizarre was the level of hopelessness and mental and emotional binds slavery. Example of this was heavily based on economic status the people we observed came under subjection with will and unhealthy pact agreements and private rituals to maintain co- dependent.

Various ranges of people observing facial expressions and verbal statements and cues of disgust due to accumulation with even of educational status and achievements. There is a groundbreaking discovery revealed and the findings prove that based on the interaction of homes civic groups and religious institutions. Many houses had addictions. Noted Religious institution gave off cult behavior and behavioral mental disorders and Sexual Abuse of Children registered was another observance.

This research has proved to be essential and remedy to bring restorative and reformative change. This can be assessed by the presentation of independent research and additional oral presentation media over 15,000 hours of study of exercised contribution of Television and Media content recorded outreaching 70,000+ people in 30 days March-April 2019 spanned actively engaged in various fields of subjects from more prominent platforms Hosting interviews on TV Networks of celebrities, actors, media producers, public relations personnel, politicians- government officials State Representatives , governors, mayors, and senators in Congress in U.S. Teachers and many other professionals from across North America USA, Canada, India, Europe, Africa over 30+ countries and as far as China, Japan and Australia through social media data. Multiple nationalities, creeds and cultures involved in this research study raising many questions about transforming the mind stronger, smarter, healthier and creating empathic behavior, mind, healing infused with implemented CCE theory in further discussion throughout the discipline research findings. This research is more real world shared. All information is not pre planned or prepped but real findings in moment and observations and recordings on many levels for Post-Doctoral research publication and to further bring change and reformation to nations in the world.

In the science of Neuroscience Oxytocin regulates behaviors of trust empathy and generous works and behavior. Anger comes with the amygdala; parts of the prefrontal cortex plays a role with anger. Deep in the brain gives behavioral and emotional responses.

Keywords: Neurological Behavior, Spiritual and Health and Wellness, Integrative Therapies Counseling, Abuse Sexual, Emotional Psychological, Education Regulation Amygdala, Mind, Homelessness, Social Behavior, Anger, Emotions, jealousy, economics, wages, life, wealth, economic base, Southern California, Los Angeles, Evil, Powers, Welfare, Intelligence, Media, Television, PTSD, Sexual Trauma, Bad Mind Obesity, Poverty, Resource Community, Economic Scale , Medicinal Balm healing Holistic Practitioner

References

Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience, Volume 10, Issue 12, December 2015, Pages 1738–1748, <https://doi.org/10.1093/scan/nsv059>

Martin, R. E., & Ochsner, K. N. (2016). The Neuroscience of Emotion Regulation Development: Implications for Education. *Current opinion in behavioral sciences*, 10, 142–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2016.06.006>

<https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/joy-and-pain/201403/envious-reactions-great-wealth>

<https://www.ocregister.com/2017/11/11/a-look-at-the-prevalence-of-mental-illness-in-california-and-the-u-s/>